

SEMANTIC ASPECTS OF TRANSLATION

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Abstract. *In our article, the problems encountered in the process of translation are aimed at highlighting the problems between closely related languages, and revealing the problems of false equivalents and their translation requires the relevance of successive translation problems between closely related languages.*

Keywords: *translation problems, translator, translation methods, interpretive translation, text, term.*

If we pay attention to the history of translation, we can recognize the 20th century as the golden age of the science of translation, despite the fact that it has a very ancient history. It is not an exaggeration to say that this century brought not only the theory of translation studies, but also the development of science and technology to a high level. It is the development of these areas, the achievement of high production goals, the increase of export and import potential, the strengthening of diplomatic relations, which led to the further popularization of synchronous and sequential types of translation studies. The development of these fields by itself drew the attention of linguists to the science of translation studies and led to the conduct of many researches. Despite the many scientific works, the theory of translation studies is included among the fields that have not yet been fully studied. The Development of the Times Several classifications of the development of translation have been proposed by various scholars. From the classifications given

by translators, we focus on the classification produced by V.N. Kommisarov in the course of our scientific research. In the course of these researches, the following opinion given by Russian scientists is still valid, i.e., "being a perfect master of two languages does not mean a perfect master." does not mean that he translated the text and speech in a completely understandable way. We believe that a translator must be able to master not only the language perfectly, but also the culture and customs of the people's way of life. It is no exaggeration to say that the translation process is not only the translation of two languages into each other, but also the exchange of culture.

The linguistic principle of translation implies, first of all, the reconstruction of the formal structure of the original. However, declaring the linguistic principle as the main one can lead to over-pursuing the translation of the original text - it becomes a literal, linguistically correct but artistically weak translation, which and it is one of the types of formalism by itself. Foreign linguistic forms are accurately translated, stylization occurs according to the laws of the foreign language. In cases where the syntactic structure of the translated sentence can be expressed in translation using similar means, word-for-word translation can be considered as the last option of translation without further literary processing. However, it is relatively rare for syntactic devices to match in two languages; often, when translated word for word, the norms of closely related languages are violated in one way or another. In such cases, we encounter a certain gap between content and form: the author's point is clear, but the form of its expression can lead to false equivalence in languages that are close to each other. A complete translation does not always reproduce the emotional impact of the original, so literal accuracy and artistry are in constant conflict with each other. There is no doubt that translation is based on linguistic material, literary translation cannot be beyond the translation of words and phrases, and the translation process itself must be based on knowledge and understanding of the laws of both languages. Compliance with the laws of the

language is mandatory for both the original and the translation. Researchers define language as the material of a work of art, and a literary translation, in his opinion, does justice to its laws, as well as the original. But to understand literary translation, as soon as linguistic means are compared, it means not to pay attention to its aesthetic side. From the point of view of the artisticness of the translation, the artisticness of the original, and the compatibility of linguistic correspondences, it serves only artistic correspondences. Therefore, the general criterion of linguistic correspondence alone cannot be used to determine the quality of a literary translation, and usefulness may not require the same degree of verbal closeness to the original during translation.

Others believe that literary translation should be considered from the point of view of word creation, that is, not from linguistic, but from literary point of view.

According to this theory, the main driving force of the translator should be the idea inspired by the original, which forces him to search for adequate linguistic means to express the ideas in words, that is, the literary translation is not linguistic, but corresponds to the original .

We do not doubt the idea that each translation as a creative process should be defined by the individuality of the translator, but the main task of the translator is to convey the original features in the translation. To create an artistic and emotional impression corresponding to the original, the translator must find the best language tools: find synonyms, suitable artistic images, etc. Speaking of translation, we think it is good to dwell on translation and its types.

When translating a term from one language to another, we may face the following difficulties;

a) Non-existence of a word that expresses the meaning of that term in the language being translated.

b) That the term being translated does not have the same meaning.

This problem can be solved only by the method of translation based on the

context.

In order to overcome these problems and make the translation process easier, we offer the following translation methods:

1) Transliteration, in this method, the term is translated in the same way as it is in the original language.

2) Transcription is the method of translation through sound forms, i.e. by pronouncing it exactly as it is said in the language being translated.

3) Translation using the Kalka method.

There is a multi-meaning expression in Uzbek language "finding a language". They say to find a way to someone's unlocked heart. This expression also expresses the fact that two people understand and know each other well about a task or problem in life and act accordingly. It also expresses the meanings of mutual agreement and agreement. It is necessary to have such an understanding between the author to be translated and his work and the translator. By finding a language, we understand the author's peculiarities and the artistic features of a particular work and organizing the process accordingly. Finding a language will be of great creative benefit only when the translator loves the author to be translated and his work, and knows that it will bring great spiritual benefit to his reader. We know that a translator always works with words. He works as a creator, linguist, and stylist in the midst of several languages. Therefore, only with the power of the translator's work and talent, the translation can sound in harmony with the original. The translator derives the meaning of the sentence and the individual words that make up the sentence only and only depending on the context and its flow, the meaning of the word to the sentence, the meaning of the sentence to the sentence, the meaning of the sentence to a separate complete fragment, and the meaning of the fragment to the work adapts to the whole content, form and style. After all, the purpose and function of a word, a sentence, and the content observed by the author are fully revealed only in the context. Each word in the language serves to express

several meanings. For example, which of the dozens of meanings of the words "have" or "eye" does the author express in the same passage, what tasks does he assign to the word? , will "open". In this, his extensive knowledge of languages and the potential of interpretation come into force. Along with these, we should also pay special attention to the problems that arise in the translation process. One of the problems of translation is that the meaning of the whole text is not limited to the sum of the meaning of its elements. The meaning given in the text is based on direct connections between denotative, connotative, stylistic, syntactic meanings of sentences, syntactic meanings of units larger than sentences, suprasegmental and lexical-semantic meanings of words and phrases. Each lexical-grammatical field has its own separate structure, and at the same time it has its own lexical, morphological and syntactic system. That is why knowing the characteristics of two languages, i.e. foreign and mother tongue, is good practical knowledge, but it is known that this is not enough for translation. In addition to knowing the characteristics of the language, the translator must also have reliable qualifications. For example, when a translator is translating from English to Uzbek, the English language belongs to the family of Germanic languages, its word order, the features of compounds, the use of tenses, the use of ambiguous words, the synonymy of words stylistically differences and pay special attention to such things, and in the process of translating into Uzbek language, that Uzbek language belongs to the family of Turkic languages, word order differs from English language, and the number of tenses in English language is less than in Uzbek language , it is necessary to take into account the presence of Arabic, Persian, Mongolian words in the lexical layer of the Uzbek language. That's why the researcher Muattar Jorayeva said, "A translator is not a draftsman, but an artist!" " published an article under the slogan.

Translation activity is divided into two types of translation, which are significantly different from each other. Translation is the transfer of the meaning of the original text into a written text in written or electronic media, taking into

account the norms and characteristics of the written language of both texts. Translation aims to transfer the meaning of the statement of the representative of the source language culture into the target language, taking into account the characteristics of oral speech in both languages. The comment is divided simultaneously and sequentially. It should be noted that sign language translation is not usually classified as a type of interpretation.

The invention of the computer helped create electronic dictionaries and later computer-aided translation programs. The translation made with their help does not include the semantic and emotional side of the text. The problems of such assistant translators are similar to self-learning artificial intelligence. Nevertheless, such tools are indispensable in translation activities, especially in large translation agencies. There are also online services for automatic translation of individual words, sentences, and entire phrases (eg Google Translate), based on statistical data on how people translate individual phrases.

The services of translation agencies are in demand in most countries of the world, because the need for translation exists in many areas of human activity. Thus, translation provides technical, business, tourism, everyday and other fields and helps overcome the language barrier for millions of people on our planet every day.

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